

Information pack

Collaboration to Harmonise the Assessment of Next Generation
Evidence (CHANGE) - 1st workshop

Oslo, 18 – 20 June 2024

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Useful contacts

Scientific program, agenda, meeting organisation	Technical information, meeting organisation, assistance, etc.	Travel arrangements (if organised by the project team)
Gro Mathisen Tel: +47 995 93 780 gro.haarklou.mathisen@vkm.no	Gisle Solstad Tel: +47 983 67 286 gisle.solstad@vkm.no	Berg-Hansen AS c/o Emilie Ilsaas +47 08050 (+47 220 0850) Emil@Berg-Hansen.no

Meeting information A to Z

Agenda

Updated agenda is forwarded by e-mail. Overview:

Date	Time	What	Where
18 June 2024	12:00 – 13:00	Registration and lunch	Nationaltheatret Konferansesenter
18 June 2024	13:00 – 19:00	Workshop	Nationaltheatret Konferansesenter
18 June 2024	19:00	Dinner	Nationaltheatret Konferansesenter
19 June 2024	09:00 - 17:00	Workshop and lunch	Nationaltheatret Konferansesenter
19 June 2024	19:00	Dinner	Coyo Restaurant, Sørenga
20 June 2024	09:00 – 14:00	Workshop and Lunch	Nationaltheatret Konferansesenter

Accommodation

If your travel arrangements have been organised by the project team, you will/have receive(d) information about flights and hotel from our travel agent Berg-Hansen AS.

Internet

Free WI-FI internet connection will be available throughout the venue, as well as in most hotels in Oslo. Outside venue, hotels and internet hotspots, you get full 5G coverage in Oslo. Be aware of roaming costs if you are a resident from outside the EU/EEA.

Lunch and refreshments

Lunch and refreshments will be offered to participants at the time indicated in the workshop agenda. Catering services will be designed to suit all dietary needs.

Registration

You have already registered as participant in the workshop. We will register you as arrived at the beginning of day 1 of the workshop, provide you with a workshop badge, and other necessary information.

Safety and security

Your security during your visit here in Oslo is our priority. Norway has a low level of crime and violent crime is uncommon. Pickpocketing and petty theft occur more frequently in major tourist areas, hotel lobbies, train and transit stations, and surrounding areas. The Oslo Central train station is an especially popular area for pickpockets and bag snatchers. Observe normal precautions when visiting Oslo.

Everyone attending the workshop should be aware that:

- Customer service staff may approach you to assist you outside, at entrance or inside the venue.
- Access to the meeting room will only be given to registered participants wearing the meeting ID badge or authorised personnel.
- Meeting rooms will be locked when not attended by the project team or customer service staff.

Your behaviour will contribute to building a safe and secure environment as follows:

- Keep only essential personal property with you at all times and do not leave any items unattended. If you need to leave your luggage or other personal belongings, please use our cloakroom service (information to be given at the venue).
- Report anything that looks unusual, suspicious, or just out of place to a member of event staff.
- Pay attention to the safety briefings and follow the instructions of event staff.

Always wear your meeting ID badge visibly.

Special assistance

The venue and most hotels in Oslo are fully accessible to disabled participants. Nevertheless, to ensure the highest levels of comfort we would appreciate a notification if you require special assistance. Please inform us in advance by using the contact details above.

Social events

There will be the two social events during the workshop, taking place on 18th and 19th of June, in the evening.

A workshop dinner will be organised at the venue on the 18th of June at 19:00 Hrs.

You are also cordially invited by the host of the workshop, the Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food and Environment (VKM), to an informal social dinner on 19th of June at 19:00 Hrs, at the [restaurant Coyo](#), Sørenga, Oslo. Please see the map in annex.

Travel

If your travel arrangements have been organised by the project team, you will (have) receive information about flights and hotel from our travel agent Berg-Hansen AS.

Most attendants from abroad will arrive at the [Oslo Airport](#).

If you go from the airport to your accommodation, or directly to the venue in Oslo, there are several possibilities:

Airport Express (Train)

[The Airport Express](#) (Flytoget) departs the airport (with some exceptions early in the morning or late in the evening) every 10 minutes to the [Oslo Central Station](#), with a few minutes walk only to most of the hotels in the vicinity (example [Thon Hotel Terminus](#), and [Thon Hotel Astoria](#)).

At the airport, follow the signs to the Airport Express. The train station is on the underground level of the airport.

Price to Oslo Central Station: NOK 240

Travel time: 19 minutes

If you use the Airport Express directly to the venue, you can only take every second Airport Express train from the airport. Look for the Airport Express train with destination Drammen.

Get off at [Nationaltheatret Train Station](#), the first stop after Oslo Central Station). The venue is in front of the train station exit ([see this map](#)).

Price to Nationaltheatret Train Station: NOK 240

Travel time: 22 minutes

Train

At the Oslo Airport Train Station, you can also take the [normal train service Vy](#) from the airport to Oslo Central Station, or the Nationaltheatret Train Station. For both destinations, look for lines

- RE10, destination Drammen (return to the airport: Destination Lillehammer)
- RE11, destination Skien (return to the airport: Destination Eidsvoll)
- R12, destination Kongsberg (return to airport: Destination Eidsvoll)

Price to both destinations: NOK 124

Travel time: 23/27 minutes

Airport Express Bus

[Flybussen Connect](#) operates the Airport Express Buss from The Oslo Airport to the City Center 24/7.

Price to Oslo Center: NOK 239

Travel time: 65 minutes

Venue

The venue is the [Nationaltheatret Conference Center](#) – [See this link for information in English](#). The venue is situated right across (25 meters) from the Nationaltheatret Train Station – one of the stops for all public transport in Oslo, also the Airport Express Train. It's in walking distance from most of the hotels in the Oslo City Center (example [Thon Hotel Terminus](#), and [Thon Hotel Astoria](#)).

For security reasons, access to the venue will only be granted to invited participants or participants whose registration has been previously confirmed by the project team. You will be requested to **register** to collect your access badge upon arrival at the venue.

Useful information and numbers

Time Zone

Norway is situated in the Central European Time zone (CET), which is GMT +1. Like in many other countries, Summertime (daylight saving time) applies in Norway: The clock is set one hour forward on the last Sunday of March, and one hour on back the last Sunday of October.

Tourist information

Oslo and the surroundings offers a variety of tourist attractions when it comes to arts, history, architecture, gastronomy and scenery.

To find out more:

- [Visit Norway](#)
- [Visit Oslo](#)

Voltage

Norway uses **Northern European electrical standards (50 hz/220–240 volts)** so converters or transformers may be required for small electrical appliances brought from home.

Pharmacies (apotek)

Pharmacies (in Norwegian: Apotek) can be found all over Oslo. Most pharmacies are open from 09:00 – 17:00, or longer if situated in a mall. The pharmacy at the Oslo Central Station is open 24/7.

Emergency services – Phone numbers

Police: 112

Medical Emergency: 113

Fire Department: 110

Emergency room – Legevakten

[Legevakten in Oslo](#) treats most injuries and illnesses that are urgent but not life threatening. Legevakten is a part of the public health care system. Legevakten is open 24/7 (even on

public holidays) and is located in [Trondheimsveien 233 \(Aker sykehus\)](#). A 24 hour pharmacy is located in the same building.

Taxi service

Taxi can be reserved 24/7 by contacting for example [Oslo Taxi on their website](#), or by phone number +47 02323.

ATM and banking hours

ATMs are known as Minibank in Norway. They can be found everywhere in the city centre. Banks (meaning those very few who are still open to the public for general banking services) are open Monday to Friday from 10:00 to 15:00. Banks are closed all day Saturday and Sunday and on national holidays. Currency Exchange services and Money Transfer services can be found at Oslo Airport and the Oslo Central Station.

Drinking water

The tap water in Norway is of excellent quality. You can drink tap water from anywhere as long as nothing else is stated.